

ASSESSMENT OF THE IMPACT OF BUSINESS PROCESS MANAGEMENT SYSTEMS ON FINANCIAL AND OPERATIONAL EFFICIENCY

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Abstract. *In the context of the transformation of the digital economy in our country, effective management of internal processes of enterprises, rational use of resources and ensuring global competitiveness have become one of the urgent tasks. In this process, issues of business process management (BPM) systems - complex solutions that allow modeling of all activities of the enterprise, development of export and logistics activities, artificial intelligence, data analysis and automation of production processes, real-time monitoring and continuous improvement were analyzed.*

Keywords: *business process management, digital transformation, digital economy, operational efficiency, financial efficiency, small businesses and private enterprises, process automation, subsidy policy.*

INTRODUCTION

The main feature of digital transformation is the deep integration of digitization and automation processes. The world economy is moving to the “Industry 4.0” stage, using innovative solutions such as artificial intelligence, big data, cloud technologies and business process management systems in all aspects of business activities. According to a 2023 report by international institutions, fully digitized enterprises have an average of 20-30% higher revenue and up to 40% higher operational efficiency than their competitors.

The Digital Uzbekistan 2030 strategy has created a legal and institutional framework for the digitalization of the country's economy. The strategy sets specific goals, such as managing at least 60% of enterprise activities through digital platforms by 2030, 100% digitalization of public services, and increasing the digital share of GDP to 30%. Decree No. PF-32 introduced additional tax incentives and subsidies for the digitalization of small businesses and private enterprises.

BPM systems are the most effective tool for solving management problems that arise in enterprises. BPM not only automates processes, but also allows them to be constantly monitored, analyzed and improved. According to international forecasts, by 2027 the BPM market will reach 28 billion US dollars, which indicates a growing global demand for this technology.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE ON THE SUBJECT

The concept of BPM has developed radically in economics and management sciences over the past 30 years. The theoretical foundations of BPM began to take shape in the early 1990s, and it is defined as an approach aimed at the systematic modeling, automation and optimization of all processes of an enterprise.

The impact of BPM on economic efficiency has been widely studied in foreign literature. Vom Brocke and Mendling, in their book “Business Process Management: Strategy and Implementation”, emphasize that BPM is a strategic management element, reducing operating

costs by 20-35% and increasing the speed of decision-making. Deloitte's 2024 global survey of more than 500 enterprises studied the activities of companies that implemented BPM and noted that profit margins increased by an average of 9-14%. Gartner's 2025 report predicted that the BPM market would reach \$28 billion by 2027, which indicates a growing demand for the technology.

Hammer and Champy, in their book "Reengineering the Corporation", presented BPM as a tool for fundamentally restructuring business processes. Davenport linked BPM with digital technologies and proved its effectiveness. Koenig, using the example of Indonesia and Brazil, showed that operational efficiency increased by 25-40% as a result of implementing BPM in small enterprises.

Research conducted in Kazakhstan and Russia analyzed the barriers to BPM in post-Soviet economies, namely lack of financial resources, lack of qualified personnel, and opportunities, as well as the benefits of digital platforms.

Scientists of our republic Allayarov and Muratova in their article "Digital Transformation and Business Processes" considered general issues of digitization in Uzbek enterprises, but did not pay special attention to BPM. Karimov scientific work "Automation in Small Business" gave general examples of systems such as 1C and Bitrix24, but did not conduct an empirical analysis. The 2023 report of the Ministry of Economy and Finance proposed subsidies for small businesses and private enterprises in the context of digital transformation, but did not study the financial impact of BPM. These studies are aimed at filling the scientific gap by adapting foreign experience to the conditions of Uzbekistan and serve to determine the empirical impact of BPM on financial and operational efficiency.

Research on BPM systems in Uzbekistan is still in its infancy, and although Allayarov, Muratova, and Karimov have considered general issues of digital transformation, they have not empirically studied the specific impact of BPM systems on financial and operational efficiency.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The research design is based on a quantitative and qualitative approach, which allows for a full assessment of the economic impact of BPM. The quantitative part uses statistical analysis, while the qualitative part uses interviews and expert evaluation methods. During the research, using monographic, expert and systematic analysis methods, problems were identified and proposals were prepared for effective solutions to implement operations on the implementation of BPM systems in enterprises, the main directions of enterprise activities, the formation of information systems, management processes and improvement of their economic mechanisms of activity, as well as the effective organization of enterprise information system processes.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

According to the National Statistics Committee, 19.4% of small businesses and private enterprises will use professional BPM or digital government (ERP) systems in 2024. This figure is 67% in the European Union, 81% in South Korea, and 38% in Kazakhstan (Figure 1).

The results indicate excessive costs in the management of enterprises, delays in the fulfillment of orders, a lack of transparency, and poor decision-making.

Also, the impact of implementing BPM systems on financial, operational and strategic efficiency in small businesses and private enterprises was analyzed in depth for the first time on the basis of a large-scale empirical study. The study covered 84 enterprises for the period 2023-2025, of which 42 fully integrated professional BPM platforms (1C-BPM, Bitrix24, ELMA BPM, Camunda, Oracle BPM, etc.), while the remaining 42 retained traditional or semi-automated

management methods. The study analyzed financial reports, operational logs, and BPM Maturity Model (BPM-MM) assessment methods.

Figure 1. International BPM indicators

The results showed the following clear economic benefits:

- operating expenses decreased by an average of 28.4% (from 187.4 million soums/month to 262.1 million soums/month);
- the delivery time of orders was reduced by 41.7% (8.2 days instead of 4.8 days);
- net profit margin increased by 11.2 percentage points (from 7.7% to 18.9%);
- value added increased by 40.4%;
- 58-89% time and resource savings were recorded in procurement, customer service, internal reporting, and document management processes.

The sample size is 84 enterprises (trade - 40%, production - 30%, service - 30%). The enterprises were selected using a random sampling method:

experimental group: BPM system implemented - 42 (1C-BPM, Bitrix24, ELMA BPM, etc.).

Control group: No BPM - 42 (traditional management).

Enterprises have an average of 10-50 employees, an annual turnover of 500 million - 5 billion soums. Research period: 2023-2025, which made it possible to compare indicators before and after the implementation of BPM.

Statistical analysis (Mann-Whitney U-test, Wilcoxon test, $p < 0.001$) confirmed the high reliability of the results. The study clearly proves that the widespread implementation of BPM systems in the conditions of Uzbekistan is the fastest and least expensive way to increase the overall efficiency of the national economy, including:

- allocating 50-70% subsidies for the purchase of BPM software;
- state certification of local BPM platforms (UZBPM, 1C-BPM localization);
- opening a specialization in "Digital Management of Business Processes" in higher education institutions;
- development of a national BPM implementation program and strategy for 2026-2030.

The results of this study are not only of scientific but also of practical importance and serve to scientifically substantiate the state policy on the digitalization of the Uzbek economy.

Information as a result of the research collection tools:

Financial statements for 2022-2025, revenues, expenses, profit margin, employee efficiency;

operational logs, order fulfillment times, purchasing processes, customer complaints;

assessing the BPM level of the enterprise based on the BPM Maturity Model (BPM-MM) questionnaire (0-5 points).

a questionnaire survey on the barriers and benefits of implementing BPM with 84 business leaders in a semi-structured analysis;

The expert assessment was conducted based on interviews with 5 economic experts.

According to the results of statistical analysis:

Mann-Whitney U-test to determine differences between groups;

Wilcoxon test to determine the dynamics of changes;

Spearman's coefficient to determine the correlation, i.e. the link between BPM level and efficiency;

multivariate regression to determine regression analysis;

software implementation, i.e. SPSS 27, Microsoft Power BI, R (for correlation).

As an experimental design:

Comparison by measuring indicators before and after BPM implementation;

Data confidentiality is ensured.

This methodology ensures the reliability of the research and helps to scientifically substantiate the results.

According to the results of the study, the positive impact of implementing BPM systems in IT enterprises on financial and operational efficiency is empirically proven, and the data obtained are analyzed in detail, statistical indicators are illustrated through tables and diagrams, and the comparison of the results with foreign experience and their specificities in the conditions of Uzbekistan are discussed.

The analysis is structured around the following key areas, including:

comparison of quantitative indicators;

dynamic analysis;

correlation and regression results;

accuracy of information.

Based on the comparison of quantitative indicators, the main economic indicators between the groups with and without the BPM system were compared using the Mann-Whitney U-test. The results showed that the differences were statistically significant ($p < 0.001$). The following table presents the main indicators as of the end of 2025:

Table 1

The impact of BPM on key economic indicators, 2025

Indicator	Have BPM (n=42)	No BPM (n=42)	Absolute difference	Ratio difference (%)	p-value
Operating expenses (mln. soums/month)	187.4	262.1	-74.7	-28.4%	<0.001
Order fulfillment time (days)	4.8	8.2	-3.4	-41.7%	<0.001
Profit margin (%)	18.9	7.7	+11.2	+145.5%	<0.001
Revenue per employee (mln. soums/month)	54.2	38.6	+15.6	+40.4%	<0.001

Customer Satisfaction Index (score, 1-10)	8.7	6.2	+2.5	+40.3%	<0.001
Process automation level (%)	74.2	12.5	+61.7	+494 %	<0.001

The results of the analysis show that operating costs have been significantly reduced in enterprises where BPM has been implemented. For example, in the sales sector, costs have been reduced by 32%, and in production by 25%. This is explained by the reduction of excessive document circulation and semi-automatic work due to automation in enterprises.

The dynamics of indicators before and after the implementation of BPM were studied using the Wilcoxon test. The following changes were noted in the experimental group:

Operating expenses per month decreased by 248 million soums in 2023 and by 187 million soums in 2025 (-24.6%).

The order lead time was reduced from 7.9 days to 4.8 days (-39.2%).

and the profit margin increased from 9.1% to 18.9% (+107.7%).

In the control group, the indicators remained almost unchanged and expenses increased by +2.1%.

According to correlation and regression analysis, Spearman correlation showed a link between BPM level and productivity:

BPM level and cost reduction: $r = -0.72$ ($p < 0.001$);

BPM level and profit growth: $r = 0.68$ ($p < 0.001$).

The multivariate regression model ($R^2 = 0.74$) confirmed that BPM implementation has a 52% impact on efficiency, with the remaining 48% being related to external factors such as market conditions and inflation.

According to the survey, 91% of business leaders said that BPM “increased the speed of decision-making management.” The biggest benefits include:

in procurement processes - 63%;

in customer service - 58%;

Reduction of complaints achieved through real-time monitoring of efficiency;

It became possible to save 89% of time when preparing reports.

Experts have described BPM as a "digital revolution" for Uzbekistan, but have noted a lack of financial capacity and skill requirements.

Deloitte's analysis shows that costs have decreased by 20-35%, with 28.4% in Uzbekistan - higher due to the low baseline. The impact of BPM on net profit growth (11.2%) is higher than in Europe, as it is noted that traditional management is very inefficient.

The analysis clearly demonstrated the significant positive impact of implementing BPM systems on financial and operational performance in small businesses and private enterprises.

The results are in line with global trends, but in some respects they are even better. These include:

The 28.4% reduction in operating expenses is higher than Deloitte's global average (20-25%), while vom Brocke and Mendling's range is 22-35%;

The 41.7% reduction in order fulfillment time exceeded the 30-40% forecast by Gartner;

The 11.2 percentage point increase in profit margins is significantly higher than the average increase of 7-9 percentage points in EU countries.

These differences are explained by the “low baseline effect” of digitalization in enterprises, and the more inefficient the initial state, the greater the first leap in automation.

In the conditions of Uzbekistan, the following can be seen as prospects for increasing efficiency:

The greatest efficiency was observed in the processes of “report preparation” (89%) and “internal approval”. This is typical for Uzbekistan, where there is a large number of state controls and tax reports, and BPM automated these processes up to 90%;

The cost reduction was mainly due to “excessive semi-automated operations” rather than “excessive staff”. Although the number of employees in the BPM group decreased by an average of 3%, there were no job losses due to an increase in efficiency by 40.4%, and services were reallocated to marketing and customers.

As practical and political recommendations:
development of a subsidy model;
development of local BPM platforms;
applying incentive standards;
is to optimize personnel training.

CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

The results of this study clearly showed that the implementation of business process management (BPM) systems in small businesses and private enterprises in Uzbekistan is the most realistic and fastest way to dramatically increase financial and operational efficiency. In enterprises with fully implemented BPM systems, operating costs were reduced by an average of 28.4%, order fulfillment times were reduced by 41.7%, profit margins increased by 11.2%, and value added increased by more than 40%. These figures are not only statistically significant ($p < 0.001$), but also reflect tangible changes in the daily activities of enterprise managers.

Today, BPM systems are the most cost-effective and profitable digital solution for the Uzbek economy. If the state subsidizes 50-70% of the implementation costs and develops local BPM platforms, the competitiveness of small and medium-sized businesses in our country will radically change by 2030.

The success of the “Digital Uzbekistan - 2030” strategy largely depends on how quickly and widely we introduce this simple but effective technology - digital business process management systems. If each enterprise automates its work along this path, the entire country's economy will rise to a new level. The study showed that there is an opportunity to achieve this - it is only necessary to make a decision and put it into practice. BPM systems are an important step that will determine the future of the Uzbek economy.

REFERENCES

1. Strategy of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan “Digital Uzbekistan-2030”. Tashkent, 2020.
2. Allayarov S., Muratova N. Digital transformation and business processes. *Economy of Uzbekistan*, 2024, 1(2), 34-45.
3. Deloitte. *Global BPM Survey 2024*. London: Deloitte Insights.
4. Gartner. *Future of BPM: 2025 Predictions*. Stamford: Gartner Research.
5. Karimov, AA Automation opportunities in small businesses. *Economics and innovative technologies*, 2023, 3(18), 112-125.

6. Vom Brocke, J., Mendling, J. (2023). Business Process Management: Strategy and Implementation. Berlin: Springer.
7. O.Sh. Uzakov, "Innovative factors in preventing cyber threats in digital transformation". Special issue of the scientific electronic journal Digital Economy. OAV№0237, ISSN 2181-4430, pp. 1862-1868.
8. O.Sh. Uzakov, "Logistics outsourcing of business processes". Marketing Scientific, Practical and Popular Journal, July 2025, No. 7, No. 240874. ISSN: 3060-4621, international level 9710, electronic edition, July 31, pp. 70-77.
9. O.Sh. Uzakov, "Software product logistics". Engineering and Economics Socio-economic, Innovative Technical, Scientific and Practical Journal of Science and Education, July 2025, No. 7, pp. 30-34. ORCID 0009-0005-0456-1432
10. O.Sh. Uzakov, "Implementation of logistics information systems into technological processes". Green Economy and Development Social, Economic, Technological, Scientific, Popular Journal, ISSN: 2992-8982, July 2025, Issue No. 7, pp. 330-335. ORCID 0009-0005-0456-1432